

THE DESCRIPTION OF LOYALTY IN “DIGITAL FORTRESS” BY
DAN BROWN

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Abstract: This article reveals an in-depth analysis of that literary work and discusses the lives of courageous individuals working for national security, and the dangers they face in their lives. Introductory section provides brief data about Dan Brown’s life and literary works and the importance of “Digital fortress” work in the world literature and the history of writing this literary work. What is more, the structure and conflict of the work, mainly characters and their loyalty are discussed, and shown in the main body. Giving detailed information, each of them is demonstrated individually. In the conclusion section all the supplied data are summarized.

Key words: Loyalty, safety system, patriotic prompt, bravery, courage, patriotism.

Introduction. Dan Brown is the writer of countless the bestseller books, each of his literary works has already become one of the best readable famous novels of all time and together with, the theme of psychic controversial among readers, specialists and scientists in the World.¹ Brown’s novels are usually declared to read in almost 56 foreign languages in every mass media around the world with over millions of copies in print when we compare with other world literary works. For instance “Digital Fortress” which is analyzed, Dan Brown came out with his first thriller in 1997, Digital Fortress on the stage of mysterious literature. He proceeded to write other literary

¹ Dan Brown. Digital fortress. Tashkent: Offset print, 2019.-p 2.

works “Angels and Demons” and “Deception Point” to attract his own readers. His one of the paradigms of the best and effective masterpieces, “The Da Vinci Code” by Dan Brown was published in March 2003 and sold nearly 6000 copies so rapidly and reached the New York Times’ Best Seller List in its very first week. It is a fact that confirms his great and unique ability in literature. Moreover, Digital Fortress by Dan Brown is a great novel of deception and betrayal in the nation's most secret and powerful authority organization of the USA, the National Security Agency. In his works we can see his endeavor at an primitive form of detective fiction set. They were looked through many times and being studied by plenty of readers and scientists of the sphere.

Literature review. This novel is called a thriller, the reason for this is that –it is a literary work that is based on fast-paced and strong motion, technological world, gives the reader great premonition, forces the reader to stay among pages and to reach the final pages. The main idea being cryptography the concentrate on the story involves many curious and eager every reader and every foreman of each field.

Dan Brown could perform this significant job at revealing the features of incantation and secretive points and intellectual data in such a way so as to give gratitude techno lovers, individuals who is really into technology and yet make the complicated topic of encryption to be so seductive and easy to grasp. Dr. M. Kalaiarasan ,who is a professor, department of English RVS college of arts and science, India, shares his own ideas in his article “Loyalty in Relationships Turned into Disloyalty in the Novels of Dan Brown”, below:

“ Dan Brown has beautifully intertwined how loyalty in relationships turns into disloyalty in these novels. Brown incorporates large amounts of information into his novels, which shows his interest in research and scholarship. In short time, he blends history and presents the development of the characters in his novels. Through the code breaking and suspense, Brown has created the true villain in an interesting manner by sustaining and garnering his abilities. The closing chapters of the novels, Brown has

created more interest and thrill in the minds of the readers. His writings are window to research in which many things are to be discovered”².

Analysis and discussion . Through central and main character Susan, we learn being brave and loyal and something about how cryptography has evolved today, as well as the NSA, its functions, capabilities, and the amazing and high-powered organization that governs the entire state of the United States. As mentioned above, the exciting foundation is fast, with a lot of skepticism, interesting characteristics, and a great plot supported by a romantic and challenging interdependence, however, “Digital Fortress” is a techno-thriller that forces the reader to explore, it is written at a very high level³.

The book explores the sense of preserving the homeland as our own, the courage of Susan Fletcher, the most professional cryptographers in the United States, her soulmate David Becker enduring mysterious threats and challenges and a detective for the National Security Agency to uncover dangerous digital secret codes feelings are revealed. This work will help every young reader to uncover the little details in this area and provide some information that all U.S. confidential information is at risk. The book conveys and explains deep thoughts to the reader within the framework of the most powerful intelligent organization in the world. The U.S. National Security Agency deals with the tampering with complex and difficult encrypted international documents and messages. They identify other people’s secrets and plans, which are associated with disrupting the state’s security system, and protecting themselves and the whole state’s citizens’ lives. In this literary work, the national agency works effectively because most Americans are unaware of its existence and functions. This poses terrible problems of privacy that computer users have been accustomed to in the digital age and era. It is in this type of safe environment that espionage can be

²https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315809135_Loyalty_in_Relationships_Turned_into_Disloyalty_in_the_Novels_of_Dan_Brown

³ <https://thisclosed.wordpress.com/characters/>.

perpetrated through computer crime, such as cybercrime, which has led to the discovery of many other crimes.

The essential and primary responsibility and liability of NSA staffs is to investigate and manage every message sent and received in the American society. This obvious ethical issue is described as a crucial problem in literary creation. Every defender, even if he is an ordinary citizen, is focused on defending his homeland like the apple of his eye, as we see in the person of one of the protagonists, David Becker. Because he unknowingly gets into a riot, during the story he learns what happened in the U.S. National Security System and what a serious situation he was given. But even if he understands everything and feels powerless to do so, he will not back down.

“...David Becker sensed in Strathmore's voice that the ring was very important, and wondered why this jewel, which had some characters, was so necessary, though he did not ask too much, to carry out the commander's command, even if it meant risking his life. It is safe to say that every his action is a true patriotic quality with other example in the below: “...David froze and was shocked, not knowing what to do as he held the phone in his hand, and all his thoughts were turned upside down. "This is a matter of national security." The commander's words echoed in his ears, but he did not understand the connection between the ordinary ring and American security. Still, Becker, well aware that Strathmore was over the age of humor, felt a sense of responsibility on his shoulders and thought for a few minutes in order to plan his work. Then, as if he had made up his mind”(page 50-52).

He could have died on the way or lost his sweetheart, Susan Fletcher. Still, in his heart, devotion, duty, love for the motherland promises to clarify the situation as much as possible, to find the necessary code for that unsolvable program.

”... Becker closed his eyes and pulled. He knew he would need a miracle to escape death. His fingers were losing their leverage. He glanced down, past his dangling legs. The drop was the length of a football field to the orange trees below. The pain in his side was getting worse. Footsteps now thundered above him, loud

leaping footsteps rushing down the stairs. Becker closed his eyes. It was now or never. He gritted his teeth and pulled” (page 166-167).

By these descriptions the author was able to create a criminal and mysterious together with the feeling of love atmosphere. The reader is intrigued and, by the way, is inclined to think what will be the end of the story. The most important thing for my research paper is that the person reading the book will be in panic and terror and in addition to this, to illustrate as a paradigm to the reader actuality and falsity behind love and respectability, predominant appreciative relationship. He or she is afraid, perhaps, ready for something horrifying to befall. In my opinion this is the reason why Dan Brown’s “Digital fortress” is called as a thriller novel.

Conclusion. It is shown in the novel that the society is vulnerable to violence, abuses and murders. So the hero David had to survive the road chase and the usage of weapons by the cruel killer in the plot of the story. The central and major characters had to co-operate with the way society is to obtain his aim. David and Susan had to tolerate with the arrogant punk because it is by doing so that their involvements in the sequence of the story are more secure and brave and indicate being strong-willed, loyal staff and generation in front of their motherland to defend it. This novel can teach every reader to be so loyal, brave, bold and gives moral lessons about how to overcome patiently any barrier that face with them.

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